

Analysing the congestion impact of deliveries schedule in urban construction sites

PROLOG Conference

La Rochelle (FR), 11/05/2017

Presented by:

Samuel RENAULT - LIST

LUXEMBOURG
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 633338.

Agenda

- Context: the SUCCESS project
- Research problem and State of the Art
- Case study: SUCCESS pilot's sites
- Data analysis
- Findings and conclusions

SUCCESS Id card

- **SUCCESS: Sustainable Urban Consolidation CentRES** for conStRuction
- **Thematic area:** Reduction of costs and negative impacts of the construction supply chain
 - **Topic:** To what extent and how can the supply chain management and Construction Consolidation Centres (CCCs) concepts bring about generic solutions to improve the construction supply chains?
- **Duration:** 36 months (Start 01/05/2015)
- **Total budget:** 3.2 M €
- **Funding:** European Commission, Horizon 2020 programme, MG-5.2-2014: Reducing impacts & costs of freight & service trips in urban areas
- **CIVITAS:** SUCCESS is one of ten H2020 projects that have been selected to become member of the network

SUCCESS consortium

Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)
Valenciaport Foundation (VPF)
Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation (ITL)
En&Tech Reseach Centre (EN&TECH)

Tralux
Federation of Construction Companies (FEVEC)
Cooperativa Muratori e Braccianti di Carpi (CMB)
Vinci Construction France (VCF)

Emilia Romagna Region (RER)
Foundation of the Valencian Community for Strategical Promotion, Development and Urban Innovation (INNDEA)
Association pour la Formation professionnelle dans les Transports (AFT)

4 Living labs:

SUCCESS concept

As Is Analysis

- Data collection
 - Construction Supply Chain understanding
 - Logistics costs allocation
- Factors identification for a viable Business Model
 - Potential saving sources
 - Stakeholders relationships (more integrated SC)
 - Incentives urban policies

Road map for a better Construction Supply Chain

➤ Replicability and take up

Methodologies and optimisation tools

- Define methods and tools to optimise the Construction Supply chain
- Develop modeling and simulation tools

To Be Analysis

- Define scenarios based on new methods and tools
 - Simulate the defined scenarios
- Design solutions
 - Operational management
 - Business models

State of the Art

- Construction business has specificities (Koskela, 1992) that impact its supply chains: one-of kind nature of projects, site production and temporary multi-organization with different interest
- With up to 30% of freight tonnage, construction represents a key segment of urban freight (Dablanc, 2009)
- Importance of on-time delivery for supply chains operations (Bushuev and Guiffrida, 2012)
- ERTRAC stresses the need for improvement of transport schedule reliability: Strategic Research Agenda for 2030 (Smit et al., 2010) & Urban Freight Roadmap (ALICE, 2015)
- JIT delivery starts to be explored for construction sites, through lean approaches (Lundesjö, 2015)

Research problem

- Cross-road
 - Urban Logistics
 - Construction sites logistics
- 1. How delivery schedules are used by urban construction sites?
- 2. How delivery schedules are respected in the urban construction logistics?
- 3. What are the **impacts** of respecting/missing delivery schedule in construction urban logistics and their specificities due to the construction sector?

Research method

- Key Performance Indicators identification
Distance (from production to site), Travel time (inside/outside the city), **Truck waiting time (inside/outside the site)**, Loading time, Congestion, **Punctuality**, Emissions (CO₂, PM)
- Data collection principles
 - Data collection grid
 - Root cause analysis
- Data collection (8 months : Jan `16 – Aug `16)
 - Daily observation on each site by dedicated worker
 - ➔ 4436 delivery / pickup observations
- Quantitative analysis & interpretation

Data collection grid

Address of the loading location
Address of the previous delivery 2
Address of the previous delivery 1
Address of next delivery 1
Address of next delivery 2
Address of final come back
Starting time from the loading location (time)
Arrival time in urban area (time)
Arrival time near the construction site (time)
Planned delivery time 1 (time)
Planned delivery time 2 (time)
Arrival time at construction site (time)
Starting time of unloading (time)
Ending time of unloading (time)
Material weight (kg)
Roundtrip or Direct trip (choice list)
Come back empty or loaded (choice list)
Vehicle Euroclass (choice list)
Vehicle Fuel type (choice list)
Gross vehicle weight rating (GVWR) (kg)
Vehicle Net weight (kg)
Vehicle surface (sqm)
Vehicle type (choice list)

Scheduled delivery time

Scheduled delivery interval

Root cause analysis (1/2)

- Aim: identify all cases of truck waiting and their causes & impact (depending on whether schedule is respected)

Root cause analysis (2/2)

- Causes of truck waiting:
 - Truck early arrival
 - Site delay
 - Time window scheduling
 - Truck delay and site unavailability
- Impacts of truck waiting:
 - Congestion on site
 - Congestion on roads nearby the site → city congestion

SUCCESS Pilots' sites

Luxembourg (Luxembourg)

- 11 400 m²
- 21 M €
- Residential, shops, offices

Paris (France)

- 55 475 m²
- 144 M €
- 1st Minister headquarter, public auditorium

Valencia (Spain)

- 7 772 m²
- 16 M €
- Railway station, park, shops

Verona (Italy)

- 85 914 m²
- 126 M €
- 2 hospitals

Data collection process

Data analysis

Data summary

- 1 site does not use delivery schedules (< 13% of deliveries)
- 3 sites use extensively delivery schedules (45% to 98% of deliveries)
 - 1 site uses only **fixed time** delivery schedule
 - 1 site uses only **time window** schedule
 - 1 site mixes both
 - 2/3 time window schedule
 - 1/3 fixed time schedule

Findings

- Site congestion vs. Road congestion
 - Highly depending on site context and organisation
 - Limiting congestion on site reports congestion on road (and the other way round?)
- Impact of time window scheduling
 - Scheduling with time window does generate congestion (1st cause of congestion on site)
but (so far) no correlation with size of the time window
- Other impacts
 - Early arrival has more impact on road congestion
 - Site lateness has more impact on site congestion

Limits & threats to validity

- Analysis based on only 4 construction sites
 - Findings need to be confirmed with a larger data set
- Data collected by « manual » observation on site
 - Although data quality controls and corrections was set up
- Specificities of sites' contexts prevent detailed comparison among the sites and generalisation of findings

Conclusions

- Managed as projects, construction sites have specific logistics and supply chains approaches
- Delivery practices are heterogeneous wrt.
 - Delivery scheduling ($\frac{3}{4}$) vs. non-scheduling ($\frac{1}{4}$)
 - Type of scheduling : fixed-time vs. time-window
- Missing the schedule leads to congestion accountable to haulier (early arrival), consignee (site delay) or both (time window schedule, late arrival and site unavailability)
 - Carefully consider the congestion impact when using time-window scheduling
- Global solutions will be explored in future steps
 - Construction Consolidation Centers (buffer zone + JIT)
 - Building Information Models (forward view on material demand, dynamic planning)

Thank you for your kind attention!

SUCCESS relevance

Urban challenges: **CO2-free city logistics in major urban centres by 2030***

- Urban freight logistics:
 - **20%** of the road congestion
 - **25%** CO2 emission (**42%** of the GHG emissions)
 - **20%** of the transportation costs

*Transport White Paper, European Commission 2011

SUCCESS objectives

- Decrease the negative externalities produced by urban freight transportation: congestion, pollution, noise and accidents
- Improve the use of the existing transport infrastructures
- Decrease building and renovating costs and impacts on urban environment
- Increase the level of cooperation and coordination among all the stakeholders of the supply chain
- Develop reusable methods and tools

Leverage: Consolidation Centre

TRL 3

TRL 5

(c) LIST - SUCCESS, 2017

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 633338.

1.c.2.a

1.c.2.b

2.a.1

2.a.2

2.b.2.a

2.b.2.b

